

INTENTIONAL SELF-REGULATION' AMONG THE FEMALE STUDENT TEACHERS.

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Abstract

The present study shows the status of intentional self-regulation among the female student teachers. The study reveals the scope for developing the self-regulation among the female student teachers. The paper discusses the dimensions of intentional self-regulation and state the importance of analysing the intentional self-regulation among student-teachers and help them to develop these skills among them.

INTRODUCTION

The future of a nation depends on the human resources of that nation. So it is very essential to empower the people with accurate, age appropriate and culturally relevant information. Education is the potential tool to develop responsible and socially productive citizen. Developing healthy attitudes and skills to respond to real life situations in positive and responsible ways among student teachers, are of great importance. The promotion of positive and socially responsible generations are in the hands of teachers. So it is very essential to equip the student- teachers in those aspects so that they will be able to mould the future citizens accordingly.

Intentional self-regulation

Intentional self-regulation describes how people make choices, plan actions to reach their goals, and regulate the execution of their actions, making processes of intentional self-regulation central to healthy human functioning. Self- regulation is a cognitive, behavioural and emotional skills that enable individuals to select and executive behaviours that are in pursuit of a particular goal.

elf-regulation (SR) is an important capacity of a person to adapt to the variety of contextual circumstances that lead to healthy development of life (Zimmerman, 2002; Gestsdottir et al., 2010). Individuals with well-developed self-regulation know how to evaluate their own abilities, monitor their work progress, make efforts strategically, and utilize opportunities in the environment to help achieve their goals (Gestsdottir et al., 2010). Individuals with higher self-regulation were also found to achieve better psychological well-being in various contexts (e.g., Caprara and Steca, 2006; Allard, 2007). In educational contexts, self-regulated learning (SRL) denotes “an active, constructive process whereby learners set goals for their learning and attempt to monitor, regulate, and control their cognitions, motivation, and behavior, guided and constrained by their goals and the contextual features in the environment” (Pintrich, 2000, p. 453). While SR and SRL share the fundamental tenets but differ in scope, at times the two terms have been used interchangeably in the literature.

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Objectives of the present study

The present study aims to examine students-teacher's levels of self-regulation.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The study includes 100 secondary student-teachers with varying teaching skills. ISR was assessed using the same version of the SOC measure as used by Gestsdottir and colleagues (2015). S (Selection) includes goals, O (Optimization) involves steps to achieve said goals, and C (Compensation) includes adjustments to challenges and barriers to maintain success in goal attainment (Baltes, Lindenberger, & Staudinger, 2006). Gestsdottir, et al. reported that, to create the SOC measure they employed, nine items were taken from the 24-item SOC measure (Freund & Baltes, 2002; Gestsdottir, Bowers, von Eye, Napolitano, & Lerner 2010). Items from three subscales (two from S, four from O, and three from C) comprise the abbreviated version of SOC (Cronbach's $\alpha=.65$ with the present sample). Participants were asked to respond to one of two options asking which type of person they are more like, Person A or B. One response was consistent with using SOC skills whereas the other response choice was inconsistent with using SOC skills. SOC-consistent responses were scored as 1 and non-SOC-consistent responses were scored as 0; all items were summed to create the abbreviated SOC scale score

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study the five factors of self-regulation, namely Goal Setting, Goal Attainment, Mindfulness, Adjustment, and Proactiveness were analysed. The present study found that four factors - Goal Setting, Goal Attainment, Mindfulness, Adjustment, are closely related to the dimensions obtained in prior studies.

Overall, the average score of the total scale lay at 4.73, moderately above the mid-point of the seven scale points. Paired-sample t-test were applied to detect mean differences between the five dimensions. Results showed that all the paired-sample t-test were significant, verifying that the participant's dimension scores, from highest to lowest are: (1) Adjustment, (2) Goal Attainment, (3) Goal Setting, (4) Proactiveness, and (5) Mindfulness. It is noticeable that Goal Setting has the standard deviation of 1.37, which is highest among the five dimensions.

Conclusion

The present study shows the status of intentional self-regulation among the female student teachers. The study reveals the scope for developing the self-regulation among the female student teachers. The intentional self-regulation shows the assimilative and accommodative behaviours and also in goal setting and goal attainment behaviours of an individual. As teachers, these are some of the desirable characteristics.

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In this study our participants scored highest on Adjustment ($M=5.13$), which means that Taiwanese college students were apt to make changes based on prior mistakes; also they think about solutions upon encountering problems. This result is consistent with Potgieter and Botha's (2009)'s study wherein South African college students scored higher in the Learning from Mistake dimension. One possible explanation of such consistency is that college students are relatively young and might be more flexible or malleable to adjust themselves (Wilson, 2008). On the other hand, Taiwanese college students scored lowest on Mindfulness ($M=4.31$), followed by Proactiveness ($M=4.60$). This means that in addition to the aforementioned problem of passivity, Taiwanese college students also suffer from poor conscious awareness, and worse, weak resolution/perseverance to follow through their plans. Such a lack of volitional control has also been reported by Kao et al. (2013) study wherein Taiwanese college nursing students ($N=537$) scored lowest on Self-management among other dimensions of self-directed learning. It is interesting that the standard deviation of Goal Setting ($SD=1.37$) was highest among all the studied variables, meaning that some students are good at planning and settings goals but others may not. It would be helpful that college instructors or mentors help students reflect on their personal aspirations, and work with them to set appropriate goals for study as well as personal lives and future growth. Our follow-up comparisons indicated that females scored higher in self-regulation total score than male students. This result is in line with Yeh et al. (2013) national study that Taiwanese female college students applied more self-regulated

In this study we yielded five factors of self-regulation, namely Goal Setting, Goal Attainment, Mindfulness, Adjustment, and Proactiveness based on a national sample of Taiwanese college students. We found that the former four factors (i.e., Goal Setting, Goal Attainment, Mindfulness, Adjustment) are closely related to the dimensions obtained in prior validation studies. For Goal Setting, Neal and Carey (2005); Pichardo et al. (2014), and Garzón Umerenkova et al. (2017) all discovered this same factor. The items such as “I have trouble making plans to help me reach goals” and “I have a hard time setting goals for myself” are commonly included under the construct of Goal Setting. On the other hand, our Goal Attainment aligns with Goal Orientation in Gavora et al. (2015) study and Internal Locus of Control by Vosloo et al. (2013). Common items under the construct of Goal Attainment include “I have personal standards, and try to live upto them” and “I'm able to accomplish goals I set for myself.” Mindfulness has been identified as an important factor across SSRQ

validation studies; for instance, Potgieter and Botha (2009) and Vosloo et al. (2013) respectively included Mindfulness and Mindful Awareness dimensions in their SSRQs. Common items include “I don’t notice the effects of my actions until it’s too late” and “I have trouble following through with things once I’ve made up my mind to do something”. While under a quite different name, Adjustment in this study resembles Learning from Mistakes coined by Potgieter and Botha (2009); Pichardo et al. (2014), and Garzón Umerenkova et al. (2017). Adjustment was also similar to Self-direction in the SRQ validation study by Gavora et al. (2015). Common items across studies include “I don’t seem to learn from my mistakes” and I learn from my mistakes. The above construct alignment between the current study and prior studies provide evidence that our TSSRQ should bear good construct and criterion-related validities. Yet, in this study Proactiveness has been perceived by Taiwanese college students as a unique factor of self-regulation. We suspect that it has been influenced by the general conception